

Index of Authors

Nur Aqilah Baseri Huddin, 82
Asma Abu-Samah, 82
Badariah Bais, 57
Charis Teoh Yi En, 1
Chia Tieng Tieng, 13
Gan Kok Beng, 1
Harhiviin a/l Ganesan, 20
Huda Abdullah, 28
Iskandar Yahya, 72
Izzuan Ismail, 40
Kalaivani Chellapan, 20
Kaliswaran a/l Ganesan, 28
Mohammad Shahidul Islam, 63
Mohammad Tariqul Islam, 63
Muhammad Khairul Naim Saaey, 47
Nik Khaliq Zailani Nik Iskandar, 57
Noorfazila Kamal, 28
Norbahiah Misran, 63
Nor Azwan Mohamed Kamari, 40
Nur Amaliea Izzatie Azmi, 82
Nurrol Athirah Mohamad, 63
Nurul Izzati Saleh, 72
Puvaneswaran a/l Chelvanathan, 57
Radin Za'im Radin Umar, 47
Sawal Hamid Md Ali, 13
Yushaizad Yusof, 47